

Statistical report

Supplemental material for... *Paper citation and DOI*

```
options(install.packages.check.source = "no", warn = -1)

# PACKAGE MANAGEMENT #####
pckgs<-c("tidyverse", "ggthemes", "ggalt", "GGally",
        "corrplot", "gridExtra", "nortest",
        "skedastic")
pckgs2Install<-pckgs[!(pckgs %in% library())$results[,1]]
pckgs2Load<-pckgs[!(pckgs %in% (.packages()))]
for(pckg in pckgs2Install) {install.packages(pckg, repos="https://cloud.r-project.org/",
                                             quiet=TRUE, type="binary")}
for(pckg in pckgs2Load) {library(pckg, character.only = TRUE)}
```

```
## — Attaching core tidyverse packages ————— tidyverse 2.0.0 —
## ✓ dplyr      1.1.3      ✓ readr      2.1.4
## ✓ forcats   1.0.0      ✓ stringr    1.5.0
## ✓ ggplot2   3.4.4      ✓ tibble     3.2.1
## ✓ lubridate 1.9.3      ✓ tidyr      1.3.0
## ✓ purrr     1.0.2
## — Conflicts ————— tidyverse_conflicts() —
## X dplyr::filter() masks stats::filter()
## X dplyr::lag()    masks stats::lag()
## i Use the conflicted package (<http://conflicted.r-lib.org/>) to force all conflicts to be
come errors
## Registered S3 methods overwritten by 'ggalt':
##   method                from
##   grid.draw.absoluteGrob ggplot2
##   grobHeight.absoluteGrob ggplot2
##   grobWidth.absoluteGrob  ggplot2
##   grobX.absoluteGrob      ggplot2
##   grobY.absoluteGrob      ggplot2
##
## Registered S3 method overwritten by 'GGally':
##   method from
##   +.gg    ggplot2
##
## corrplot 0.92 loaded
##
##
## Attaching package: 'gridExtra'
##
##
## The following object is masked from 'package:dplyr':
##
##   combine
```

```
# DATA IMPORT ####
dfDadesC <- read.table("CleanData146.txt", sep="\t",
                      dec=",", na.strings = "NA", quote="",
                      colClasses = c(rep("character",6), rep("numeric",13)),
                      encoding="latin1", header=T)

summary(dfDadesC)
```

```
##      DATA          PROD          CODE          FA
## Length:146      Length:146      Length:146      Length:146
## Class :character Class :character Class :character Class :character
## Mode  :character Mode  :character Mode  :character Mode  :character
##
##
##
##      LER          DESCRIPTION          pH          MASS_LOSS_105
## Length:146      Length:146      Min.   : 4.94      Min.   : 0.29
## Class :character Class :character 1st Qu.: 8.03      1st Qu.:21.79
## Mode  :character Mode  :character Median : 9.51      Median :27.49
##                                     Mean  : 9.71      Mean  :30.80
##                                     3rd Qu.:11.69    3rd Qu.:36.71
##                                     Max.  :13.03    Max.  :81.34
##                                     NA's  :1
##      LOI          AT4          TOC          COD
## Min.   : 1.15      Min.   : 0.075      Min.   : 1.30      Min.   : 34
## 1st Qu.:16.77      1st Qu.: 0.488      1st Qu.: 8.20      1st Qu.: 501
## Median :20.69      Median : 1.786      Median :11.93      Median : 1404
## Mean   :24.78      Mean   : 6.858      Mean   :15.05      Mean   : 4105
## 3rd Qu.:27.89      3rd Qu.: 9.116      3rd Qu.:18.03      3rd Qu.: 3938
## Max.   :69.60      Max.   :67.199      Max.   :91.17      Max.   :46151
##                                     NA's  :16      NA's  :4
##      BOD          BIO          DOC          VOL_INOC
## Min.   : 1.0      Min.   : 0.35      Min.   : 94      Min.   : 0.000
## 1st Qu.: 87.0      1st Qu.: 9.05      1st Qu.: 1120     1st Qu.: 1.600
## Median : 252.0     Median :13.65      Median : 2564     Median : 3.200
## Mean   : 510.3     Mean   :19.52      Mean   : 5721     Mean   : 7.236
## 3rd Qu.: 590.0     3rd Qu.:26.79      3rd Qu.: 6375     3rd Qu.: 9.750
## Max.   :3120.0     Max.   :51.05      Max.   :45500     Max.   :52.000
## NA's   :6          NA's   :6          NA's   :24
##      MASS_SAMPLE      MASS_DRY      VOL_SAMPLE
## Min.   : 2.0      Min.   : 1.968      Min.   : 1.40
## 1st Qu.: 20.0     1st Qu.: 15.132     1st Qu.: 15.62
## Median :100.0     Median : 44.397     Median : 56.00
## Mean   :105.1     Mean   : 70.299     Mean   : 77.58
## 3rd Qu.:200.0     3rd Qu.:120.291     3rd Qu.:131.00
## Max.   :300.0     Max.   :238.716     Max.   :286.00
##
```

```
# ADDITIONAL VARIABLES ####
dfDadesC$logAT4 <- log(dfDadesC$AT4)
dfDadesC$logMASS_DRY <- log(dfDadesC$MASS_DRY)
dfDadesC$pH2 <- dfDadesC$pH ^ 2
dfDadesC$INOC <- dfDadesC$VOL_INOC>0

# NORMALITY TEST ####
ad.test(dfDadesC$AT4)
```

```
##
## Anderson-Darling normality test
##
## data: dfDadesC$AT4
## A = 14.007, p-value < 2.2e-16
```

```
ad.test(dfDadesC$logAT4)
```

```
##
## Anderson-Darling normality test
##
## data: dfDadesC$logAT4
## A = 2.5734, p-value = 1.592e-06
```

```
# CORRELATION TESTS AMONG BIODEGRADABILITY MEASURES ####
vars <- dfDadesC[,c(10,9,11:15)]
colnames(vars) <- c("$AT[4]", "LOI", "TOC", "COD",
                  "$BOD[5]", "$BOD[5]/COD", "DOC")

corrplot(cor(vars,use="pairwise.complete.obs",
             method="spearman"),
         method="shade", addCoef.col = "black",
         col = colorRampPalette(c("#FF6666", "white", "#6666FF"))(100),
         tl.col="black", tl.cex = .8)
```



```

png("Figures/FigNN_CorrShade.png", width=3500, height=3000, res = 600)
corrplot(cor(vars,use="pairwise.complete.obs",
  method="spearman"),
  method="shade", addCoef.col = "black",
  col = colorRampPalette(c("#FF6666", "white", "#6666FF"))(100),
  tl.col="black", tl.cex = .8)
dev.off()

```

```

## png
## 2

```

```

corrplot.mixed(cor(vars,use="pairwise.complete.obs",
  method="spearman"), tl.col="black",
  lower.col= "#333333", tl.cex = .8)

```



```
png("Figures/FigNN_CorrMixed.png", width=4000, height=4000, res = 600)
corrplot.mixed(cor(vars,use="pairwise.complete.obs",
  method="spearman"), tl.col="black",
  lower.col= "#333333",tl.cex = .8)
dev.off()
```

```
## png
## 2
```

```
round(cor(vars, method="spearman", use="pairwise.complete.obs"),3)
```

```
##          $AT[4]  LOI  TOC   COD $BOD[5] $BOD[5]/COD  DOC
## $AT[4]      1.000 0.158 0.061 -0.148 -0.094      0.007 -0.357
## LOI         0.158 1.000 0.502 0.038 0.076      0.050 0.087
## TOC         0.061 0.502 1.000 0.011 0.031      0.150 0.294
## COD        -0.148 0.038 0.011 1.000 0.824     -0.353 0.612
## $BOD[5]    -0.094 0.076 0.031 0.824 1.000      0.173 0.458
## $BOD[5]/COD 0.007 0.050 0.150 -0.353 0.173     1.000 -0.109
## DOC        -0.357 0.087 0.294 0.612 0.458     -0.109 1.000
```

```
round(cor.mtest(vars, method="spearman", use="pairwise.complete.obs")$p,3)
```

##	\$AT[4]	LOI	TOC	COD	\$BOD[5]	\$BOD[5]/COD	DOC
## \$AT[4]	0.000	0.056	0.489	0.079	0.271	0.936	0.000
## LOI	0.056	0.000	0.000	0.655	0.369	0.558	0.338
## TOC	0.489	0.000	0.000	0.906	0.729	0.094	0.002
## COD	0.079	0.655	0.906	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
## \$BOD[5]	0.271	0.369	0.729	0.000	0.000	0.041	0.000
## \$BOD[5]/COD	0.936	0.558	0.094	0.000	0.041	0.000	0.236
## DOC	0.000	0.338	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.236	0.000

AT4 vs BIO

```
ggplot(dfDadesC, aes(x=BIO, y=AT4,
                    color=factor(ifelse(AT4>10,2,ifelse(AT4>5,1,0))))) +
  geom_point(shape=3) +
  geom_hline(yintercept = 5, color="orange") +
  geom_hline(yintercept = 10, color="red") +
  scale_color_manual(values=c("green","orange","red")) +
  scale_y_continuous(trans="log",
                    minor_breaks = c(.1,.2,.5,1,2,5,10,20,50,100),
                    breaks= c(.1,.5,1,5,10,50,100)) +
  annotate("text",x=52, y=12, label="European Draft Limit",
         hjust=1, color="red", size=2.5)+
  annotate("text",x=52, y=6, label="German Limit",
         hjust=1, color="orange", size=2.5)+
  labs(y=parse(text="AT[4]*', '*mg~O[2]~~g^-1~DM"),
       x=parse(text="BOD[5]/COD*', '*100~%'")) +
  theme_classic()+
  theme(legend.position = "none",
        panel.border = element_rect(color="grey", fill=NA),
        axis.text=element_text(color="black"))
```



```
ggsave("Figures/Fig01_AT4vsBIO.png", device="png", dpi=600,
        units="px", width=3500, height = 3000)
```

```
# AT4 MODELLING #####
fit1 <-lm(logAT4~pH+pH2+logMASS_DRY,dfDadesC)
summary(fit1)
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = logAT4 ~ pH + pH2 + logMASS_DRY, data = dfDadesC)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -3.5307 -0.5987  0.1324  0.6970  2.5795
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept) -3.26567    2.21695  -1.473  0.142966
## pH           1.83527    0.45881   4.000  0.000102 ***
## pH2          -0.10940    0.02385  -4.587  9.82e-06 ***
## logMASS_DRY -0.82327    0.09410  -8.749  5.90e-15 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 1.032 on 141 degrees of freedom
## (1 observation deleted due to missingness)
## Multiple R-squared:  0.6621, Adjusted R-squared:  0.6549
## F-statistic: 92.08 on 3 and 141 DF,  p-value: < 2.2e-16
```

```
plot(fit1, which=1)
```



```
plot(fit1, which=2)
```



```
plot(fit1, which=5)
```



```
lillie.test(fit1$residuals)
```

```
##  
## Lilliefors (Kolmogorov-Smirnov) normality test  
##  
## data: fit1$residuals  
## D = 0.069597, p-value = 0.08236
```

```
breusch_pagan(fit1)
```

```
## # A tibble: 1 × 5  
##   statistic p.value parameter method alternative  
##   <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <chr> <chr>  
## 1 2.21 0.529 3 Koenker (studentised) greater
```

```
dfModel <- cbind(dfDadesC[!is.na(dfDadesC$pH),],  
                predict.lm(fit1, interval="confidence"))  
  
# AT4 vs DRY MATTER #####  
## ALL data #####  
ggplot(dfDadesC, aes(x=MASS_DRY,y=AT4)) +  
  geom_smooth(method="lm", formula=y~x, se=F,  
              color="grey") +  
  geom_point(shape=3, alpha=0.8) +  
  scale_x_continuous(trans="log",  
                    minor_breaks = c(1,2,5,10,20,50,100,200,500),  
                    breaks= c(1,2,5,10,20,50,100,200,500))+  
  scale_y_continuous(trans="log",  
                    minor_breaks = c(.1,.2,.5,1,2,5,10,20,50,100),  
                    breaks= c(.1,.5,1,5,10,50,100)) +  
  labs(y=parse(text="AT[4]*", '*mg~O[2]~g^-1~DM'),  
       x="Dry matter, g") +  
  theme_classic() +  
  theme(panel.border = element_rect(color="grey", fill=NA),  
        axis.text=element_text(color="black"))
```



```

ggsave("Figures/Fig02_DMA11.png", device="png", dpi=600,
        units="px", width=3500, height = 3000)

## In two groups ####
sep <- 17.5
ggplot(dfDadesC, aes(x=MASS_DRY,y=AT4, group=MASS_DRY<sep)) +
  geom_smooth(method="lm", formula=y~x, se=T,
              color="black") +
  geom_smooth(method="lm", formula=y~1, se=F,
              color="grey", linetype="dashed") +
  geom_point(shape=3, alpha=0.8) +
  scale_x_continuous(trans="log",
                    minor_breaks = c(1,2,5,10,20,50,100,200,500),
                    breaks= c(1,2,5,10,20,50,100,200,500))+
  scale_y_continuous(trans="log",
                    minor_breaks = c(.1,.2,.5,1,2,5,10,20,50,100),
                    breaks= c(.1,.5,1,5,10,50,100)) +
  labs(y=parse(text="AT[4]*", '*mg~O[2]~g^-1~DM'),
       x="Dry matter, g") +
  geom_vline(xintercept = sep, color="black",
             linetype="dotted")+
  theme_classic() +
  theme(panel.border = element_rect(color="grey", fill=NA),
        axis.text=element_text(color="black"))

```



```
ggsave("Figures/Fig03_DMTwoSections.png", device="png", dpi=600,
        units="px", width=3500, height = 3000)
```

```
fit2 <-lm(logAT4~logMASS_DRY+pH+pH2,
          dfDadesC[dfDadesC$MASS_DRY<sep,])
summary(fit2)
```

```
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = logAT4 ~ logMASS_DRY + pH + pH2, data = dfDadesC[dfDadesC$MASS_DRY <
##   sep, ])
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -2.5195 -0.4095  0.1714  0.5496  1.8651
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)  3.830059   5.191593   0.738   0.464
## logMASS_DRY -0.426148   0.287925  -1.480   0.146
## pH          -0.024563   1.129084  -0.022   0.983
## pH2         -0.001465   0.061668  -0.024   0.981
##
## Residual standard error: 0.8748 on 46 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.04653,    Adjusted R-squared:  -0.01565
## F-statistic: 0.7483 on 3 and 46 DF,  p-value: 0.529
```

```
plot(fit2, which=1)
```



```
plot(fit2, which=2)
```



```
plot(fit2, which=5)
```



```
lillie.test(fit2$residuals)
```

```
##  
## Lilliefors (Kolmogorov-Smirnov) normality test  
##  
## data: fit2$residuals  
## D = 0.13787, p-value = 0.01859
```

```
breusch_pagan(fit2)
```

```
## # A tibble: 1 × 5  
##   statistic p.value parameter method alternative  
##   <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <chr> <chr>  
## 1 6.51 0.0891 3 Koenker (studentised) greater
```

```
fit3 <- lm(logAT4 ~ logMASS_DRY + pH + pH2,  
           data = dfDadesC[dfDadesC$MASS_DRY > sep,])  
summary(fit3)
```

```
##  
## Call:  
## lm(formula = logAT4 ~ logMASS_DRY + pH + pH2, data = dfDadesC[dfDadesC$MASS_DRY >  
##   sep, ])  
##  
## Residuals:  
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max   
## -2.90022 -0.62305  0.03474  0.65973  2.19284   
##  
## Coefficients:  
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)      
## (Intercept) -7.51555     2.62971  -2.858  0.00528 **    
## logMASS_DRY -0.37745     0.16585  -2.276  0.02521 *     
## pH           2.27635     0.50727   4.487 2.10e-05 ***   
## pH2          -0.13100     0.02608  -5.024 2.51e-06 ***   
## ---  
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1  
##  
## Residual standard error: 1.035 on 91 degrees of freedom  
##   (1 observation deleted due to missingness)  
## Multiple R-squared:  0.4344, Adjusted R-squared:  0.4158   
## F-statistic: 23.3 on 3 and 91 DF, p-value: 2.804e-11
```

```
plot(fit3, which=1)
```



```
plot(fit3, which=2)
```



```
plot(fit3, which=5)
```



```
lillie.test(fit3$residuals)
```

```
##  
## Lilliefors (Kolmogorov-Smirnov) normality test  
##  
## data: fit3$residuals  
## D = 0.054248, p-value = 0.7029
```

```
breusch_pagan(fit3)
```

```
## # A tibble: 1 × 5  
##   statistic p.value parameter method alternative  
##   <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <chr> <chr>  
## 1 15.7 0.00133 3 Koenker (studentised) greater
```

```
# AT4 vs pH #####
ggplot(dfDadesC, aes(x=pH,y=AT4)) +
  geom_smooth(method="lm", formula=y~poly(x,2), se=F,
             color="grey") +
  geom_point(shape=3, alpha=0.8) +
  scale_y_continuous(trans="log",
                    minor_breaks = c(.1,.2,.5,1,2,5,10,20,50,100),
                    breaks= c(.1,.5,1,5,10,50,100)) +
  labs(y=parse(text="AT[4]*", '*mg~O[2]~g^-1~DM')) +
  theme_classic() +
  theme(panel.border = element_rect(color="grey", fill=NA),
        axis.text=element_text(color="black"))
```



```
ggsave("Figures/Fig04_PH.png", device="png", dpi=600,
       units="px", width=3500, height = 3000)
```

```
# INOCULUM INDEPENDENCE ####
table(dfDadesC$INOC)
```

```
##
## FALSE TRUE
## 17 129
```

```
wilcox.test(dfDadesC$logAT4~dfDadesC$INOC)
```

```
##  
## Wilcoxon rank sum test with continuity correction  
##  
## data: dfDadesC$logAT4 by dfDadesC$INOC  
## W = 1205.5, p-value = 0.508  
## alternative hypothesis: true location shift is not equal to 0
```

```
by(dfDadesC$logAT4,dfDadesC$INOC, median)
```

```
## dfDadesC$INOC: FALSE  
## [1] 1.196646  
## -----  
## dfDadesC$INOC: TRUE  
## [1] 0.5150367
```

```
ggplot(dfDadesC, aes(y=AT4,x=INOC)) +  
  geom_jitter(shape=3, color="black", width=0.2, height=0,  
             alpha=0.8) +  
  geom_boxplot(outlier.color = NA, color= "black", fill= "white",  
             alpha=0.5, size=0.2) +  
  scale_y_continuous(trans="log",  
                   minor_breaks = c(.1,.2,.5,1,2,5,10,20,50,100),  
                   breaks= c(.1,.5,1,5,10,50,100)) +  
  scale_x_discrete(labels=c("Without added inoculum (n = 17)", "With added inoculum (n = 12  
9)")) +  
  labs(y=parse(text="AT[4]*", '*mg~0[2]~g^-1~DM'), x="") +  
  theme_classic()+  
  theme(panel.border = element_rect(color="grey", fill=NA),  
        axis.text=element_text(color="black"))
```



```
ggsave("Figures/Fig05_INOCULUM.png", device="png", dpi=600,  
units="px", width=3500, height = 3000)
```